

Effects of microclimatic fluctuation and soil factor on the yield of cereal Crops grown in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract-: Climate change, soil type and extensive cultivation have been and continue to be, the principal source of fluctuations in global food production in countries of the developing world and is of serious concern in Nigeria. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the effects of fluctuation in microclimate and soil factor on the yield of major cereal crops grown in Kano state, Nigeria. Secondary data from 2008-2017 in respect to annual yield of major cereals crops (Maize, Millet, Rice, Sorghum and Wheat ($t\ ha^{-1}$) and microclimate (temperature, rainfall and relative humidity) were collected from Kano State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA) and Nigeria Metrological Agency Kano for the period under review. Soil characterization was also carried out to determine the soil texture, pH, electrical conductivity, cation exchange capacity, total nitrogen, exchangeable bases and organic matter content of the soil using standard methods. The results indicated variation in yield of the cereal crops in correspondence with variation in microclimatic data recorded during the period under review. The highest yields of these crops were observed in 2010, 2014, 2016 and 2017, when the amount of rainfall (mm) and relative humidity (%) were also in relatively highest amount. However, the least yields were recorded from 2008-2009, when the amount of rainfall (mm) and relative humidity were in relatively low amount with high temperature ($^{\circ}C$). The high degrees of variability of these climatic factors have a positive relationship with the yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of the major cereal crops produced in Kano, Nigeria. The information obtained from this study may assist in planning ahead for improved cereals crop production in Kano state Nigeria, thereby providing a strong base for sustainable food security.

Keywords: Cereal crops, Fluctuation, Microclimate, Soil, Yields;

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1.0 Introduction

Nowadays, Cereal grains have been considered as the major component of human diet over years and have played a major role in shaping human civilization. Globally, rice, wheat, and maize, and to a lesser extent, sorghum and millets are important staples critical to daily survival of billions of people. More than half of the world daily caloric intake is derived directly from cereal grain consumption (Isah *et al.*, 2015). Cereal crops are reported to be members of the grass family *Poaceae* grown for their hard seeds, which are used mainly for food that are rich in carbohydrates and contain reasonable amounts of protein, as well as some fat and vitamins (Sokoto *et al.*, 2016).

The growth and development of cereals (maize, sorghum, pearl millet, wheat and rice) is greatly affected by variations in rainfall, temperature and relative humidity as well as soil factors. Global climate changes have led to fluctuation in rainfall

and temperature pattern, and also loss in existing nutrients available to crops in the Soil which is the nutrient store-house that provides support for plant growth in various ways. The primary productivity of cereals in most areas in the northern part of Nigeria is grossly affected due to the drought-like situation and consequently unusual fluctuation pattern in some microclimatic factors such as rainfall, relative humidity, temperature and light intensity, (Mohammed *et al.*, 2014).

Cereal farming in Northern Nigeria, especially around Kano, is a major source of income and act as source of employment opportunities directly in farms and indirectly in most food industries, hence vital for economic growth and food security in the country. Climatic and soil factors remain the major factors that drive agriculture and there is every need to assess the relationship that exist between the two entities and crops production. For this rationale, this study was therefore designed to assess the impact of fluctuation

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pattern in microclimatic parameters (temperature, relative humidity and rainfall) and soil factors on cereal crops production in Kano State, Nigeria, towards putting in place measures that will minimize possible economic costs of producing these crops and help to ensure food security in spite of the fluctuation of these microclimatic factors in the area.

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Description of the Study Area This research study was conducted at Nigeria Police Academy (POLAC) in Wudil Local Government Area of Kano State Nigeria, which is located in East Central area of Kano State, and in the central area of Kano Region between longitude $8^{\circ} 45'E$, as well as between latitude $11^{\circ} 37'N$ and latitude $11^{\circ} 56'N$. Wudil is 35Km from Kano along Kano-Maiduguri road (see Fig.1). The town is located in the Kano Close Settled Zone with high population density of 350 persons per Km^2 . By tropical African standard the pressure on agricultural land is high (Mortimore, 1991). Wudil Local Government has two Tertiary Institutions of which POLAC is one of them, and it's a regimented Institution which embodies a rich diversity of cadets from the 36 states of the federation.

Figure 1; Showing Wudil LGA (The study area)

2.2 Annual yields and climatic data collection and sources

The study was designed to collect secondary data that cover a period of 10 years (2008 – 2017) in respect to annual yields of the major cereal crops (Maize, Millet, Sorghum, wheat and Rice) from Kano State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA), and the data on climatic factors (temperature, rainfall and relative humidity) from National Metrological Agency Kano.

2.3 Experimental design, Soil sampling and Analysis

Three experimental plots (I, II, and III) were established and plot I was designated for the

cultivation of Maize and Millet, plot II for Sorghum and Wheat while plot III for the cultivation of only Rice. The paired crops were not planted in the mixed cropping system but were rather planted within the sub-units of each designated plot.

The composited (bulked) soil samples were taken from each of the three plots in the study area using a soil auger of 0-30cm in depth and 0-5cm in diameter, and debris on the top soil were removed before samples were collected. The bulked soil samples were mixed thorough, sieved with a 2mm meshed wire and were oven-dried at $70^{\circ}C$ for 24 hours and analyzed chemically for Organic carbon, Organic matter, Total nitrogen, available soil Phosphorus, soil pH, Electrical conductivity, sand/silt/clay using standard methods described by Black *et al.* (1965); Allen *et al.* (1977); Bremer (1965); Mehlich (1962); Peech (1965) and Allen *et al.* (1977). And the soil samples were also physically analyzed for Soil structure and texture at the Department of soil Science faculty of Science Bayero University Kano.

3.4 DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics; Spearman correlation (r) analysis was used to test the co-relationships between the microclimatic and soil factors and the crops yields. And also Regression analysis was used as a predictive model for the crops yield in relation to climatic and soil factors using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Climatic factors and crops yield

The result on some microclimatic factors; annual mean rainfall (mm), maximum temperature ($^{\circ}C$), minimum temperature ($^{\circ}C$) and relative humidity (%) of the study area as from 2008 to 2017 is presented in Table 1. The result showed variations in these environmental factors from year to year. The trend of the rainfall recorded over the decade in the study area showed remarkable fluctuation all through the years. The amount of rainfall increased from 2008 to 2010 (760 to 1017.6 mm respectively), and started decreasing from 2011 to 2014 (880.4 to 1042 mm respectively) and finally increased after a year to 2017. The peak of the rainfall was recorded in 2016 (1053.2 mm). The result also showed how the relative humidity of the area increased (87%) with increased rainfall in 2016 whereas, the highest temperature ($^{\circ}C$) in 2013

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was recorded against low amount of rainfall (874.6 mm) and percentage relative humidity (78.6%).

The cereal crop yield per hectare ($t\ ha^{-1}$) in Kano during the period under review from (2008-2017) is presented in Table 2. The results indicated variation in grain yield of the cereal crops in correspondence with the variation in microclimatic data (rainfall, temperature, and relative humidity) recorded during the period under review. The highest yields of these crops were observed in 2010, 2014, 2016 and 2017, when the amount of rainfall (mm) and relative humidity (%) were also in relatively highest amount. However, the least yields of the crops were recorded from 2008-2009, when the amount of rainfall (mm) and relative humidity were in relatively low amount with high temperature ($^{\circ}C$) recorded during the period. Out of the five cereal crops, Rice was reported to have the highest yield all the years amongst others.

4.2 Soil physicochemical Analysis

The results for physicochemical analysis of the soil samples in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano state is presented in Table 3. The chemical characteristics across the three plots revealed that the pH and electrical conductivity (Ec) values range from 6.82 to 7.10, and 0.009 to 0.014ds/m with a mean value of 6.92 and 0.011ds/m respectively.

The organic matter content of the soils as organic carbon ranges from 1.86 to 2.42g/kg, with a mean value of 2.15g/kg, the soil total nitrogen (TN) also ranged from 0.2 to 0.5g/kg with a mean value of 0.2g/kg, whereas the available phosphate values ranged from 18.14 to 21.0 mg/kg with its mean value at 19.38mg/kg.

The exchangeable bases and cation exchange capacity ranged from 0.027 to 0.037 cmol/kg, 0.039 to 0.05 cmol/kg, 0.18 to 0.24 cmol/kg, 2.17 to 3.42cmol/kg and 2.22 to 2.40 cmol/kg for potassium (K), sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), magnesium (mg) and cation exchange capacity (CEC) respectively, with a respective mean value of 0.032, 0.043, 0.206, 3.05, and 2.44 all measured in cmol/kg across the three plots.

The physical characteristics showed the soil textural class to be sandy loam, with sand composition ranging from 72% to 92%, that of silt from 8% to 17% and clay 3% to 5%, with respective mean values of 83%, 13% and 4% across the three plots in the area of study.

4.3 Discussion

4.3.1 Effect of rainfall and temperature variation on the yield of major cereal crops (maize, millet, rice, sorghum and wheat) grown around the study area.

Agriculture process had been reported by Sokoto *et al*, (2016) to dependent highly on climatic factors which are determinant factors for the distribution of crops and their productivity. In the study area (Kano), the average temperature of the area has increased by 3.65 $^{\circ}C$ from 2008 to 2009 and further increased by 3.75 $^{\circ}C$ from 2010 to 2011. This increase in average temperature of the area has severely affected the yield ($t\ h^{-1}$) of the major cereals in Kano state Nigeria most especially in 2008, 2009 and 2011 resulting in the low productivity (yield) of the crops in the area. Monson *et al*, (1992) and Rahelah *et al.*, (2014) also reported that extreme high temperature can decrease the mean photosynthetic rate and biomass of most cereals especially wheat. There were also evidences of high inter- annual fluctuation of rainfall over decades in the study area. The high degree of this variability in rainfall has a strong positive relationship with the yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of the major cereal crops produced in Kano. The average precipitation (rainfall) of the area was highest (1053.5 mm) in 2016, and (1046.5 mm) in 2017 but it fluctuates greatly from year to year owing to sharp increase in the mentioned years with the corresponding high yield of those cereal crops produced in the area, most especially rice which is hydrophilic (water-loving) in nature. Abrol and Ingram (1996); Adams *et al*, (1998) and McCarl *et al*, (2001) similarly reported that, fluctuation in environmental temperature and precipitation will reduce yield and affect the quality of food crops thereby aggravating the situation in to food insecurity in the area.

4.3.2 Effects of Physicochemical Properties of Soil on the Yield of Major Cereal Crops Grown Around Kano State Nigeria

The yield of the crops is also dependent on the type of soil, existing nutrients and proper tillage. The characterization of the soil analysis in the study area was carried out with respect to particle size, soil pH, cation exchange capacity, electrical conductivity, and organic carbon, and total nitrogen, available phosphorous and exchangeable bases. The important observation during the study is that, the soil parameters analysed were fluctuating from plot to plot in the study area. The mean pH of the soils was 6.92, indicating that the soil is slightly acidic, which is reported to be as a result of organic decomposition and with the

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persistence application of ammonium (NH₄) nitrogen fertilizers by the farmers, Umeri *et al*, (2017). The slightly acidic nature of the soil is reported to be suitable for the production of cereal crops in the area, Lawal *et al*, (2013). More so, the nutrient status of the soils was found to be in moderate amount of total nitrogen, available phosphate, exchangeable potassium (K) and calcium (Ca) as compared to the one reported by Umeri *et al*, (2016) in rainforest zones of Delta state, Nigeria and with the critical values. The soil

analysis of the study area also revealed the textural class of the soil to be sandy-loam which is accounted for by the low clay and silt contents of the soil in the study area. This indicates that the rate of water percolation and infiltration in these soils may be high and consequently, that the water holding potentials of these soils may be low. These characteristics may predispose those soils to the process of erosion, particularly in the semi-arid region of northern part of Nigeria.

Table 1: Decade summary of climatic parameters (2008-2017) considered during the study.

Year	Rainfall (mm)	Maximum Temperature (°C)	Minimum Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)
2008	760	36.44	20.3	77
2009	730.4	31.17	17.5	83
2010	1017.6	33.33	20.15	82
2011	880.4	35.9	23.9	82.5
2012	944.8	36.47	22.79	81.4
2013	874.6	37.08	22.5	78.6
2014	1042.2	36	22	84
2015	896.9	38	23.4	87
2016	1053.2	36	23.3	87
2017	1046.5	36.1	22.91	84

Source: Nigeria meteorological agency Kano (2018)

Table 2: Crop yield (t ha⁻¹) of major cereal crops produced in the study area (2008-2017)

Year	Maize	Millet	Rice	Sorghum	Wheat
2008	2.88	1.21	3.05	1.82	2.18
2009	2.61	1.72	2.91	1.56	2.32
2010	2.97	1.77	3.51	2.23	2.40
2011	2.61	1.73	2.91	1.59	2.53
2012	2.69	1.77	3.51	2.23	2.24
2013	2.77	1.82	3.62	2.3	2.35
2014	2.85	1.88	3.8	2.37	2.47
2015	2.94	1.93	3.91	2.44	2.59
2016	2.95	1.94	3.93	2.45	2.61
2017	3.3	2.01	7.23	3.46	2.68

Source: Kano State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (2018) Note: t ha⁻¹ = Tons per hectare.

Table 3: physicochemical properties of analyzed soil within Nigeria police academy

Soil physicochemical	Plot			
pH: Electrical Conductivity (ds/m)	6.84	7.10	6.82	6.92
Organic Carbon(g/kg)	0.010	0.014	0.009	0.011
Total Nitrogen(g/kg)	1.86	2.42	2.17	2.15
Available Phosphorus(mg/kg)	0.19	0.23	0.20	0.20
Potassium, Sodium & Calcium (cmol/kg)	18.14	21.00	19.00	19.38

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Cation Exchange Capacity (cmol/kg)	0.027	0.037	0.032	0.032
Magnesium (cmol/kg)	0.039	0.050	0.040	0.043
Sand (%)	0.18	0.24	0.20	0.206
Silt (%)	2.22	2.70	2.40	2.44
Clay(%)	2.71	3.42	3.02	3.05
	92	72	85	83
	17	8	14	13
Textural Class	3	5	4	4

5.0 Conclusion

Cereal farming in Northern Nigeria, especially around Kano, is a major source of income and act as source of employment opportunities directly in farms and indirectly in flour and food processing industries, as well as in breweries. Agriculture is vital for economic growth and very important for food security in the country. Climatic and soil factors remain the key drivers of agriculture and there is a need investigating and understanding the relationship that exist between the two entities. Soil being the main source of nutrients for crops, also provides support for plant growth in various ways and health of soils can be assessed by the quality and stand of the crops grown on them. This is a general assessment made by most farmers, however scientific assessment is possible through detailed physical, chemical and biological analysis of the soils. For this rationale, this study was therefore designed to assess the impact of variability of microclimatic parameters (temperature, relative humidity and rainfall) and soil factors on cereal crops production in Kano State, Nigeria, towards finding mitigating measures which will be put in place to minimize possible economic costs of producing these crops and to help improve food security in spite of the fluctuation of these microclimatic factors in the area.

Author Contribution

The author's contributed equally

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest declared

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